

Conference report – Legal and economic perspectives of energy cooperatives' development in Poland and other countries

Tomasz Marzec

PhD Candidate, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań (Poland)

Abstract

Aim of the international conference on-line Legal and Economic Perspectives of Energy Cooperatives' Development in Poland and Other Countries was an attempt to determine, whether the legal provisions that are in force in different countries encourage citizens to establish energy cooperatives and to conduct economic activity in this legal form. 27 speakers took part in the conference. They represented 18 academic centers and 11 countries. Issues raised in presentations during the conference were a part of the global discussion on the transformation of energy systems in order to stop climate change. Speakers also highlighted how local communities benefit from the common use of the renewable energy installations, owned by citizens. The most widely discussed topic was a legal framework for conducting economic activity by energy cooperatives in different states. Presentations also included an economic analysis of the factors for the development of energy cooperatives at the local and national level.

L'objectif de la conférence internationale en ligne Perspectives juridiques et économiques du développement des coopératives d'énergie en Pologne et dans d'autres pays était de déterminer si les dispositions légales en vigueur dans différents pays encouragent les citoyens à créer des coopératives d'énergie et à mener une activité économique sous cette forme juridique. 27 intervenants ont pris part à la conférence. Ils représentaient 18 centres universitaires et 11 pays. Les questions soulevées dans les présentations lors de la conférence s'inscrivaient dans le cadre du débat mondial sur la transformation des systèmes énergétiques afin d'enrayer le changement climatique. Les intervenants ont également souligné comment les communautés locales bénéficient de l'utilisation commune des installations d'énergie renouvelable, propriété des citoyens. Le sujet le plus discuté a été le cadre juridique pour la conduite d'une activité économique par les coopératives d'énergie dans différents États. Les présentations comprenaient également une analyse économique des facteurs de développement des coopératives d'énergie au niveau local et national.

Conference report

The international conference on-line *Legal and Economic Perspectives of Energy Cooperatives' Development in Poland and Other Countries* took place on 27th May 2021 in Faculty of Law and Administration, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań. Due to the restrictions caused by COVID-19 epidemic, the conference was a virtual meeting. The audience had access to the proceedings through a YouTube online stream. All sessions were held in English.

The conference was organised by members of the Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Protection Law and of the Department of Public Economic Law. Prof. UAM dr hab. Aneta Suchoń was a Chair of the Organizing. Prof. Krzysztof Zmijewski Association for Efficiency supported the conference as its Partner. Organisational works were consulted with the International Cooperative

Alliance. Also, the event was organized under the Honorary Patronage of the Cooperative Europe and the European Federation of Citizen Energy Cooperatives (REScoop).

The conference was officially opened by AMU Deputy Rector prof. dr. hab. Zbyszko Melosik and by the Dean of Faculty of Law and Administration, AMU prof. dr. hab. Tomasz Nieborak. Opening speeches were also delivered by: Mr. Dirk Vansintjan, the President of REScoop, prof. dr hab. Roman Budzinowski, the Chief of the Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Protection Law and the President of the Polish Association of Agrarian Lawyers, Prof. Dr. Hagen Henry, Chairman of the International Cooperative Alliance Co-operative Law Committee, Dr. Andreas Wieg, Head of the German Office for Energy Cooperatives (DGRV) and Mr. Rafał Czaja, President of Prof. Żmijewski Association for Efficiency.

The aim of the conference was an attempt to determine, whether the legal provisions that are in force in particular countries encourage the citizens to establish energy cooperatives and to conduct economic activity in this legal form. The speakers also tried to determine, what factors – mainly legal and economical – influence the development of energy cooperatives.

The event was divided into three panels. First of them was moderated by Prof. Dr. Roland Norer, representing the University of Lucerne. The first part of the conference was opened by prof. UAM dr hab. Aneta Suchoń (Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań) with the presentation *Legal, economic and environmental aspects of functioning of energy cooperatives – introductory consideration*. The speech included describing the key terms for the conference subject (i.a. energy cooperative, renewable energy sources, energy security) and the presentation of the cooperative sector in Poland. Then Prof. Dr. Thomas Schomerus from Leuphana Universität Lüneburg gave thoughts on subject – *Renewable Energy Requirements in the Building Sector - advantage for energy cooperatives?* Further, prof. dr hab. Marzena Czarnecka (University of Economics in Katowice) has brought the topic – *Citizen energy communities in the scope of Polish and European regulations*. Prof. UJ dr hab. Tomasz Długosz (Jagiellonian University) has answered the following question – *Creating a regulatory framework for energy communities in Poland - some legal challenges?*

Subsequently Dr. Andreas Wieg (Philipps-University Marburg) addressed the audience with the consideration – *The role of energy cooperatives in the German energy transition*. The representative of the REScoop – Mrs. Sara Tachelet presented the subject: *Energy Democracy: European citizens taking ownership of the energy transition*. After that prof. KUL dr hab. Piotr Zakrzewski (The John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin) continued with the consideration about the Polish legal system, with the speech - *Energy cooperative as a new sub-type of cooperative in Polish cooperative law*. The first panel was closed by dr. hab. Maciej M. Sokołowski (University of Warsaw, University of Tokyo) with deliberation – *Cogeneration and energy communities: cogenatives and cogenmunities (co-CHPs)*. Dr hab. Maciej M. Sokołowski had also undertaken the role of the moderator of the second panel. In the discussion that took place after the presentations in the first panel, the main subject were the differences between the Polish regulation of energy cooperatives and the legal provisions in force in other countries – mainly in Germany. The speakers have also expressed their views on the challenges that energy communities in Europe will have to face.

The first speaker in the second panel was Dr. Martin Lowery, the U.S. Representative to the board of the International Cooperative Alliance, with the speech: *The historic success and future of electric*

cooperatives in the United States. Then, Dr. Chiara Candelise (Imperial College London) presented report – *Status and evolution of the community energy sector in Italy*. Subsequently, Dr. Hui-Tzu Huang, affiliated with National Taiwan University gave the speech titled: *Public Participation in Renewable Energy: Diversified Business Models of Citizens' Power Plants in Taiwan*. After that, Dr. Lars Holstenkamp (Leuphana Universität Lüneburg) delivered a presentation: *The cooperative model in Germany's energy sector - remarks on its evolution, diffusion and success criteria*. Research team, created by Prof. Dr. Valeria Jana Schwanitz, Prof. Dr. August Wierling (Western Norwegian University of Applied Sciences), dr .Wit Hubert and PhD Student Tadeusz Rudek (Uniwersytet Jagielloński), introduced a case study to the audience: *The development of citizen-led energy projects in former Eastern Bloc countries - The case of Poland*. The last speech in the second panel was delivered by Dr. Ifigeneia Douvitsa, (Hellenic Open University): *The legal framework of energy cooperatives in Greece*. In the discussion, which followed the presentations, speakers have assessed the legal provisions regulations that are in force in the national legal systems and their changes over the years.

The third session was moderated by prof. UAM dr hab. Katarzyna Leśkiewicz. Last part of the conference was started by an individual report of Dr. August Wierling – *Energy cooperatives in Denmark - A statistical exploration*. After that dr Grzegorz Maśloch (SGH Warsaw School of Economics, Prof. Krzysztof Żmijewski Association for Energy Efficiency) delivered a speech entitled *Energy Cooperatives as an instrument towards the energy transition in Poland - social, economic and organizational conditions*. Another research team, created by prof. dr. hab. Jacek Dach, Dorota Kula (Poznań University of Life Sciences) and Ewa Woźniak (Dynamic Biogas), presented the analysis on the subject: *The exploitation of innovative biogas plant by group of farmers*. Dr. Aleksandra Łakomiak representing Wrocław University of Economics and Business shared the deliberation entitled: *Civic energy in an orchard farm - prosumer and energy cooperative - a new approach to electricity generation*.

Subsequently Prof. Dr. Antonios Maniatis (University of Patras) presented a speech: *Energy CO-OP icon*, in which he considered the importance of regulation of the energy cooperatives for the development of these entities. In the next presentation, Prof. Dr. Minko Georgiev and Prof. Dr. Boryana Ivanova (Agricultural University – Plovdiv) gave remarks on the topic: *Cooperatives in Bulgaria - integration and circular economy*. After that PhD Student Tomasz Marzec (Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań) presented a paper: *Legal determinants of energy cooperatives' development in Poland*. The last speech was delivered by PhD Student Koldo Martina Sevillano (University of Vigo), on *Energy cooperatives and social vulnerability*. After the presentations Chair of the Organizing Committee prof. UAM dr hab. Aneta Suchoń made closing remarks in order to summarise the proceedings and officially closed the conference.

As a result of the discussion, the speakers have formulated a joint conclusion, according to which energetics – in particular based on renewable energy sources - is an area of activity that opens up great opportunities for the modern cooperative sector. The remarks made during the conference speeches also revealed the image of energy cooperative movement in Europe as a phenomenon diversified in terms of territories. According to the presented papers - energy cooperatives play an important role in the energy transformation in Western European countries such as, for example, Germany. As for the countries of Central and Eastern Europe and the Balkans, only individual energy cooperatives operate there. Presented papers proved how important is favourable institutional and legal environment for the dynamic development of community energy, as well as the historical development of cooperative movement in different countries. Reports on the social importance of energy

cooperatives also showed how important can be the impact of these organizations on local communities. Cooperative initiatives in the area of renewable energy sources allow entities involved in them to obtain financial benefits and also strengthen the ties of the local communities.

In conclusion – 27 speakers took part in the conference. They represented 18 academic centers and 11 countries. The issues raised in the presentations are a part of the global discussion on the transformation of energy systems in order to stop climate change. The speakers also highlighted how many benefits local communities have from the common use of the renewable energy installations, owned by citizens. The most widely discussed topic was a legal framework for conducting economic activity by energy cooperatives in particular states. The presentations also included an economic analysis of the factors for the development of energy cooperatives at the local and national level. The presented papers will be published in writing as part of the post-conference publication. The profiles of the speakers and other information are available on the conference website.¹

¹ Online International Conference: Legal and Economic Perspectives of Energy Cooperatives' Development, source: www.cooperatives.home.amu.edu.pl.